
ATTITUDE OF UNDERGRADUATE COLLEGE STUDENTS TOWARDS VOLUNTARY “HIV/AIDS” TESTING

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Abstract

The present research study was undertaken to investigate attitude of undergraduate college students towards voluntary “hiv/aids” testing and how it is influenced by social category and academic stream. Descriptive survey method was employed for the present investigation. The sample of 355 undergraduate college students from Kangra, Hamirpur, Una and Bilaspur district of Himachal Pradesh were taken as convenient sampling along with incidental sampling technique. Attitude Scale towards Voluntary HIV/ AIDS Testing developed by Sood and Sood (2012) was used to gather the data. The data were analyzed with the help of descriptive statistics. The findings of the study are there was no significant difference in attitude of UG level students towards voluntary HIV / AIDS testing with respect to their social category. The UG level college students belonging to general, SC and OBC categories have similar type of attitude towards voluntary HIV/AIDS testing. There was no significant difference in attitude of UG level students towards voluntary HIV / AIDS testing with respect to their academic stream. The UG level college students studying in arts, science and commerce academic streams have similar type of attitude towards voluntary HIV/AIDS testing and the educational implications have been discussed in the end of the research paper.

Keywords: HIV/AIDS, Attitude, UG Level Students.

Introduction

Today, the major socio-economic problem being faced by India is poverty. Even after six decades of independence, the country is still fighting against the social evil of poverty. It is estimated that nearly one third of Indian population of 1.21 billion i.e. 426 millions of people are living below poverty line. Poverty is a phenomenon which implies a dehumanizing condition in which people are unable to look after the basic needs. Many go without a meal a day. In addition, prevailing poverty increases illiteracy. Thus, due to poverty and illiteracy, there is uncontrolled growth of population of India. Though governments are struggling hard to eradicate poverty, but the increasing population and mismanagement of government schemes have fueled the growth of poverty. Population is growing at an alarming rate. Presently, India is the second largest populated country in the world. It is estimated that the country's population will increase to about 1.26 billion by the year 2016. Whatever progress is made, is offset by the increasing population as production is not as much as the progress in population. Increase in the population is not a single problem, but it is a root of all other problems like poverty, population explosion, unemployment, terrorism, corruption, high inflation rates and environmental problems. The rapid growing population and economic development is also leading to a number of environmental issues in India because of the uncontrolled growth of urbanization and industrialization. Environmental issues include various natural hazards, particularly cyclone, floods, poor agricultural practices, loss of biodiversity, global warming, pollution and so on. If such environmental deterioration will remain continue for a longer time, then whole of the nation will turn into a barren land. Besides these major problems, India is facing today the epidemic of HIV/AIDS just like other developing countries of world. The spread of HIV in India is primarily restricted to the southern and north-eastern regions of the country. As of today, millions of Indians have been diagnosed with AIDS, millions have died in less than 15 years, AIDS has become the principal killer of all Indians between the ages of 15 and 49. It has also been found recently that even Indians do not have generic protection against the AIDS virus. Because of lack of awareness among individuals; talking about such issues is considered a taboo, even the parents do not talk about HIV/AIDS openly to their children. We do not have sex education in schools. So, a proper awareness about HIV/AIDS is must and conservatism about HIV should be dispelled. Everyone needs to know about AIDS because it waits at everyone's door. Each of us must learn how to prevent infection with HIV, how to support people around us who are HIV infected, and how national, state and local governments should deal sensibly with HIV/AIDS. Hiding behind the veils of cultural superiority is not an option. AIDS is sexually transmitted disease and has to be tackled accordingly. HIV & AIDS are both sexually transmitted diseases with fatal consequences. Human immunodeficiency virus is a virus that infects humans. A person with HIV is infected for life and can infect other. The virus attacks the immune system of humans and slowly weakens the body's defense against diseases. An HIV infected person can look and feel well for a long time without developing AIDS (Advanced stage of HIV infection). In the majority of developing countries like India, families are the primary caregivers when somebody falls ill. Presently not all family responses are supportive. HIV positive members of the family find themselves stigmatized and discriminated against within the home and in the community. Physical and social isolation at home and community, blocked entry to common facilities, blocked entry to public places, denial of death rituals and blocked access to spouse, children and other relatives represents negative attitude of individuals towards HIV/AIDS patients. There is concern that women and non-heterosexual family members are more likely than children and men to be mistreated. Kelly et. al. (1987) found that the students held negative and prejudiced attitudes towards both the AIDS and homosexual patients. This finding

suggests that medical educators should recognize that many students have stigmatizing, negative attitudes towards homosexuals and patients with AIDS. These educators should promote greater sensitivity, knowledge and understanding among medical students of those at risk for AIDS and AIDS patients. Orubuloye (1993) observed that women's apparent success in refusing unwanted intercourse was attributable to their economic-independence and strong lineage ties. It was further noted that knowledge regarding HIV prevention, acquisition, transmission and consequences of infection was high among female participants. Bhende (1994) observed that the lesser prevalence of premarital sexual activity in females can be attributed to the cultural importance given to virginity and the stigma associated with an out-of-wedlock pregnancy. Moreover, girls are subjected stricter parental control. Galbraith et.al. (1994) found that well known factors such as peer pressure, increasing levels of social interaction with the opposite sex and even household factors like broken homes and poverty, contribute to increased sexual activity and promiscuity. Bharat (1996) found that although a majority of those who had shared their HIV status with their families received care and support, it was largely men rather than women who qualified for such care. Forms of discrimination against women with HIV included being refused shelter; being denied a share of household property, being denied access to treatment and care; and being blamed for a husband's HIV diagnosis especially when diagnosis was made soon after marriage. Bhatt and Dhoundiyal (1996) found that 20-25% of Indian youth have expressed favourable attitudes towards premarital sex, with the rate being substantially higher among males, urban youth and more highly educated. Bhalla (1997) suggested that with the revolution of technology, the Internet is increasingly being employed as a portal for disseminating information, through discussion forums, e-mail counselling and web information. Corporate companies and call centres have joined hands in the fight against HIV/AIDS by organising in-house AIDS awareness programmes for their employees, almost all of whom are young. The initial lead in this direction was taken up by the Confederation of Indian Industry (CII), which began to incorporate HIV/AIDS prevention activities into its social development activities in the work place. Lal et. al. (2000) reported that among college students in the state of Kerala (in South India), those from urban areas demonstrated a more favourable attitude towards AIDS. Massawe et. al. (2001) determined the acceptability of counseling and testing and participation in a mother-to-child HIV-1 transmission intervention study using antiretroviral therapy. It was found that out of 68%, only 16.7% of enrolled women disclosed their positive HIV serostatus to their sexual partners. The main reasons for not disclosing the HIV serostatus were fear of stigma and divorce. Sixty percent of informed sex partners agreed to be tested for HIV and 69% tested HIV positive. Ganguli et. al. (2002) concluded that a number of false notions in relation to modes of transmission have been elicited. These include modes of transmission of the virus, such as drinking water, sharing utensils, using common swimming pools and insect/mosquito bites. Mehra et. al. (2002) revealed that a survey carried out among male urban slum youth in Delhi, which employed qualitative techniques such as focus group discussions, in addition to quantitative evaluation, boys as young as 17 years were found to be visiting brothels. It was also seen that sexual relationship tended to be secretive with limited condom usage.

Objectives

1. To study the attitude of undergraduate college students towards voluntary HIV/ AIDS testing.
2. To study social category-wise difference in attitude of undergraduate college students towards voluntary HIV/ AIDS testing.
3. To study academic stream-wise difference in attitude of undergraduate college students towards voluntary HIV/ AIDS testing.

Hypotheses

1. There will be no significant difference in attitude of UG level college students towards voluntary HIV/AIDS testing in relation to their social category.
2. There will be no significant difference in attitude of UG level college students towards voluntary HIV/AIDS testing in relation to their academic stream

Tool

Attitude Scale towards Voluntary HIV/ AIDS Testing developed by Sood and Sood (2012).

Research Method Adopted

'Descriptive Method of Research' was used by the researcher for investigation.

Sampling

The sample of the present study comprised of 355 UG level college students of four districts namely; Kangra, Hamirpur, Bilaspur and Una districts of Himachal Pradesh. These students were selected from 10 colleges situated in these four districts through convenient sampling along with incidental sampling technique.

Statistical Technique Employed

Descriptive statistics and 't'- test was used to analyze the data.

Findings and Results

Attitude of UG Level College Students towards Voluntary HIV / AIDS Testing in relation to their Social Category

The means of attitude scores of UG level college students towards voluntary HIV/AIDS testing with respect to their social category along with number, S.D. and t-value are given in Table 1.

Table 1
Attitude of UG Level College Students Towards Voluntary HIV/AIDS Testing in Relation to their Social Category

Table with 6 columns: Group of Students, N, Mean, SD, SE_DM, t-Ratio. Rows show comparisons between General, SC, and OBC categories.

NS: Not Significant

From Table 1, it is evident that all the computed values of 't' i.e., 0.558 (Gen. vs. SC), 0.446 (Gen. vs OBC) and 0.097 (OBC vs SC) for finding out the significance of mean differences in attitude towards voluntary HIV/AIDS testing of UG level college students...

Attitude of UG Level College Students towards Voluntary HIV / AIDS Testing in relation to their Academic Stream

The means of attitude scores of UG level college students towards voluntary HIV/AIDS testing with respect to their academic stream along with number, S.D. and t-value are given in Table 2.

Table 2
Attitude of UG Level College Students Towards Voluntary HIV/AIDS Testing in Relation to their Academic Stream

Table with 6 columns: Group of Students, N, Mean, SD, SE_DM, t-Ratio. Rows show comparisons between Arts, Science, and Commerce streams.

NS: Not Significant

From Table 2, it is evident that all the computed values of 't' i.e., 1.424 (Arts vs Science), 0.034 (Arts vs Commerce) and 1.322 (Science vs Commerce) for finding out the significance of mean differences in attitude towards voluntary HIV/AIDS testing of UG level college students...

Conclusions and Educational Implications

There was no significant difference in attitude of UG level students towards voluntary HIV / AIDS testing with respect to their social category. The UG level college students belonging to general, SC and OBC categories have similar type of attitude towards voluntary HIV/AIDS testing. There was no significant difference in attitude of UG level students towards voluntary HIV / AIDS testing with respect to their academic stream. The UG level college students studying in arts, science and commerce academic streams have similar type of attitude towards voluntary HIV/AIDS testing. The HIV / AIDS awareness and related content matter needs to be introduced in the curriculum at senior secondary level onwards. This may prove to be beneficial for improving awareness among the next generation. The facilities for HIV / AIDS testing need to be enhanced in all health centres across the country so that the youth can be made sensitive towards it and they could accept the testing conveniently. The role of mass media in the context of enhancing awareness and moulding favourable attitude towards HIV / AIDS patients among students and general public can be of very great significance. Both print and non-print media can be used to the optimum level for this purpose. The teachers can bring favourable attitude towards HIV / AIDS and its related content among students through different co-curricular activities. These activities may include nukkadnataks, skits, songs, poem recitation, quiz competition etc. The role of panchayati raj organizations in bringing awareness for voluntary HIV / AIDS testing among general public can be very useful. This will also help in reducing social stigma regarding HIV / AIDS and building a cohesive and inclusive society.

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